

Identification and Analysis of Polymer Blend in Dehydrochlorinated Poly(Vinyl Chloride)-Poly(Oxy Propylene Oxy Isophthaloyl-Co-Oxy Propylene Oxy Fumaroyl) Cryogenic Foam

M. JAYABALAN and T. BALAKRISHNAN

Department of Physical Chemistry, University of Madras, A C. College Campus, Madras-600 025

Heat and impact resistant plastic foam of dehydrochlorinated poly(vinyl chloride) (DHPVC)-poly(oxy propylene oxy isophthaloyl-co-oxy propylene oxy fumaroyl) (PPPF) was prepared for cryogenic insulation in liquid propellant tanks of space vehicle. The foam was prepared by the method of hot compacting and chemical blowing. High temperature resistant, high tensile strength and optimum impact resistant foams were obtained by the formation of crosslinked DHPVC-CO-PPPF copolymer and the blend DHPVC/PPPF/DHPVC-CO-PPPF during the process of foaming. The copolymer and the blend were separated individually from the plastic foam. The effect of foaming period on the crosslinking of DHPVC and PPF was studied by determining the swelling value and \bar{M}_n of the copolymer. The compatibility of DHPVC and PPF was investigated by uv, ir and DSC studies. The effect of \bar{M}_n of the copolymer on the compatibility was studied by DSC.

SEVERAL plastic foams were used in cryogenic insulation¹. Considering the strength to weight ratio, low density foams ($<100 \text{ kg/m}^3$) were used for space cryogenic tanks. However, medium density foams also find increasing use in the insulation and structural design of bottom bulk head panel of conventional cylindrical tank. This inordinate penalty of weight increment in bottom bulk head panel is admitted to eliminate the mechanical failure of the insulation which is due to differential thermal contraction between the foam material and the base material attached to the foam¹, tank pressurization² and outgassing³. During the stage of tanking, chill down, and top off to 95% level, differential thermal contraction between foam material and base material attached to the foam occurs in all sections of the insulated design¹. The conventional cryogenic container is a cylindrical tank which contains a cylindrical panel and bottom bulk head panel (Fig. 1). The design of the bottom bulk head may be considered as thin shell of revolution^{4,5}. The circumferential stress is greater than the longitudinal stress in the cylindrical panel. The cylindrical panel which is insulated with low density foams can experience higher differential thermal contraction. This ultimately decreases the higher circumferential stress. Therefore, the mechanical failure along the direction parallel to the axis of the cylinder may be eliminated. But the higher thermal contraction of low density foams actually alters the stress balance in the bottom bulk head panel where the circumferential and longitudinal stresses are uniformly distributed over the wall thickness. This induces mechanical failure in bottom bulk head panel. Moreover, during tank pressurization, the bottom

bulk head panel experiences higher temperature gradient in comparison to the cylindrical panel⁶. Under this condition low density foams undergo higher differential thermal contraction which then accelerates the earlier failure in bottom bulk head panel. Another possibility for mechanical failure of low density foams is outgassing. As pressure is reduced within the insulation system during ascent of space vehicle outgassing of materials in the system begins. Before the initially trapped gas is completely vented, it is partially replaced by material of outgassing vapour. The outgassing begins shortly after lift-off. The sources of the outgassing are absorbed surface gases, entrapped gases, low molecular weight fragments and sublimation of basic high polymer. Due to outgassing, honey comb delamination occurs in low density foams very easily³. But the medium density foams are found to have and experience lower differential thermal contraction⁶ and higher resistance to delamination. Therefore, the medium density foams are suitable for the insulation of bottom bulk head panel. Moreover, in insulated cryogenic tanks, the inner container or the thin walled shell must be kept apart from the outercasing by supports⁷. This may be achieved by the use of load bearing material, which may be the insulant itself. The tension supports are the easiest to design, compared to compression supports. With well designed tensile members the supports tend to stretch or deform before complete failure and the remainder still offer some support to the inner vessel. Therefore, tension supports are widely preferred. The foams, which are used as tension supports should have high ultimate tensile strength, and impact strength.

Dedicated with fondness to Prof. J. N. Mukherjee in celebration of his 90th birthday.

An attempt was made to achieve these higher mechanical properties and medium density through

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of cryogenic tank. 2(a): tank, 2(b): cylindrical panel, 2(c): bottom bulk head panel (section of a thin shell of revolution).

polymer blending. Two medium density plastic foams, viz., dehydrochlorinated poly(vinyl chloride)-poly(methyl methacrylate), (DHPVC-PMMA), and dehydrochlorinated poly(vinyl chloride)-poly(oxy propylene oxy isophthaloyl co-oxy propylene oxy fumaroyl), (DHPVC-PPPF), were prepared from the incompatible homopolymers of plasticized poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC), poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) and unsaturated copolyester, poly(oxy propylene oxy isophthaloyl-co-oxy propylene oxy fumaroyl) (PPPF) without the external addition of compatibilizers. Thermal modification of PVC and formation of DHPVC/PMMA/DHPVC-hydrogen bond-PMMA blend in DHPVC-PMMA foam in the process of foaming were reported elsewhere⁸. The present paper deals with the identification and analysis of polymer blend in DHPVC-PPPF cryogenic foam.

Experimental

Preparation of DHPVC-PPPF foam :

For the optimum performance as insulating material, an optimised composition in the formula

(Table 1) was adopted to get the desired DHPVC-PPPF plastic foam. The foaming compound was prepared by mixing the components in the same order as in the formula. PVC resin powder was preheated at 60° for 5 min to drive off the surface moisture and to condition the resin particle for fast

TABLE 1—COMPOSITION FOR THE PREPARATION OF DHPVC-PPPF FOAM

Material	Amount (pbw)
1. Poly(vinyl chloride)—Jai Enterprises, Madras, India.	100.0
2. Tricresyl phosphate—Plasticizer.	45.0
3. Poly(oxy propylene oxy isophthaloyl-co-oxy propylene oxy fumaroyl)—Reichold Chemicals, Madras, India.	90.0
4. Benzoyl peroxide—Initiator	5.0
5. Ba-Cd stearate (1 : 1)—stabilizer and surfactant	4.0
6. Aluminium chloride—curing agent and blowing agent moderator	10.0
7. Palmitic acid—surfactant	9.0
8. Silicone oil—foam controller	1.0
9. Calcium carbonate—filler	12.0
10. Paraffin wax	5.0
11. Calcium carbonate blowing agent	3.0
12. Cyanuric chloride (1.7 : 1.0 : 1.3)	4.0

absorption of plasticizer. Dry blending was carried out with PVC and tri-cresyl phosphate (TCP) at 80° for 0.5 hr, and preblending was carried out with the other ingredients without applying heat as mentioned below. PPPF was added to the dry blended, plasticized PVC and then the whole mixture was transferred to the laboratory type ball mill and mixed for 10 min under 100 rpm. All other ingredients were added subsequently and the whole mixing in the ball mill was done in not more than 45 min. The particle size of the resultant homogeneous mixture was approximately 150 μ (100 BBS).

The foaming compound was softened at 100 \pm 2° for 0.5 hr at 25 \pm 5psi pressure and then compacted in an open top paper cup of 2.5 cm diameter and 12 mm thickness. The foaming was then effected in an air oven at 200° for 1 hr. The foam was then ovencooled and preserved for testing.

Testing of DHPVC-PPPF foam :

The density was determined with the specimen of 1 in cube using weight-volume relationship (ASTM D 1622-63). The tensile specimens were prepared as per the method 'B' of ASTM D 1623-64. The specimen was adhesively bonded to the loading fixtures with the mixture of Araldite 6097 and Hardner HZ 945. The adhesive was then cured at 60° for 68 hr. Instron Universal testing machine was used with crosshead speed of 0.5 cm/min and chart speed of 20 cm/min. Izod impact tests were carried out on the notched specimen of 1 cm² area of cross section and 7 cm length. Notch depth of 2 mm was made. Avery Izod impact testing machine was used with striking velocity of 2.44 metres/sec. (ASTM C 589-68). Resistance to heat was determined by ASTM D 2126-66. The foam was found to excel in

these properties. This would have been due to the formation of polymer blend. Therefore the separation and analysis of copolymer and blend was carried out.

Analysis of copolymer and blend :

The compatibility of the present polymers was attempted in the presence of compatibilizer. The compatibilizer, cross linked DHPVC-CO-PPPF, was aimed to produce simultaneously along with foaming. The generated copolymer was anticipated to blend the remaining DHPVC and PPPF. The generation present cross linking and \bar{M}_n of copolymer may be controlled by the period of foaming. The initial period of 0.5 hr of foaming period was exploited to generate enough unsaturation in PVC which facilitated cross linking catalytically with the unsaturated copolyester resin. Therefore, the identification and analysis of the blend first deals with the copolymer and then with the blend.

Separation of (i) DHPVC, (ii) PPPF, (iii) DHPVC-CO-PPPF and (iv) blend :

(i) The plasticizer and stabilizer were removed from the 0.5 hr foamed mass by the method of Harsaw *et al.*⁹. DHPVC was separated using THF as solvent and methanol as nonsolvent. It was vacuum dried at 60°.

(ii) After the separation of DHPVC, the copolyester (PPPF) was separated using benzene as solvent and isobutanol as nonsolvent from the remaining residue. The molecular weight of PPPF was determined by vapour phase osmometry in DMF.

(iii) The foam samples, subjected to the foaming period of 40, 50, 60, 70 and 80 min, were then subjected to solvent extraction. The plasticizer and stabilizer free samples were treated with THF-C₆H₆ mixture. The free homopolymer, DHPVC and copolyester were extracted combinedly. To the remaining residue THF was added and the copolymer, DHPVC-CO-PPPF, was extracted and reprecipitated in methanol. The molecular weight of the copolymers was also determined by vapour phase osmometry in DMF. The swelling value of the copolymers in the 40, 50, 60, 70 and 80 min foamed samples was determined to determine the extent of cross linking. A mixture of acetone (A.R. grade) and carbondisulfide (1 : 1 v/v) was used as swelling solvent. Swelling value was determined as per the method 'swelling in solvent vapours' reported by Dannenberg *et al.*¹⁰. The copolymer formed at 40 min foaming period was taken as the initial copolymer to be further cross linked (since cross linking started after 30 min) and the swelling value of this sample was determined after exposure to solvent vapour. The swelling values of the remaining samples were determined from the initial weight which is equivalent to that of the copolymer formed at 40 min foaming period and from the weight of the sample exposed to solvent vapour.

The percent grafting and number of grafting sites in the copolymers derived from 40, 50, 60, 70 and 80 min foaming period were determined using the expressions :

$$\text{Percent graft cross linking} = \frac{\text{Wt. of the graft crosslinked homopolymer}}{\text{Wt. of the homopolymer to be graft crosslinked}} \times 100$$

and

$$\text{Number of graft crosslinking sites} = \frac{\text{Wt. of graft crosslinked homopolymer/molecular wt. of the homopolymer}}{\text{Wt. of the second homopolymer used/molecular wt. of the second homopolymer used}}$$

(iv) The blend DHPVC/PPPF/DHPVC-CO-PPPF was then separated from the samples of 40, 50, 60, 70 and 80 min foaming period. The deplasticized and stabiliser free samples were treated with THF, the blend extracted and reprecipitated with methanol. The blend was then vacuum dried at 60°. DHPVC, copolymer and the blend which were derived from steps (i), (iii) and (iv), respectively were subjected to absorption spectral analysis.

The unsaturation present in DHPVC, copolymer and DHPVC/PPPF/DHPVC-CO-PPPF blend was determined by absorption spectra using DMF. The unsaturation in DHPVC was also determined by the method of titration (ASTM D 2849-71). The sample was reacted with mercuric acetate and methanol to produce acetoxy mercuric methoxy compounds and acetic acid. The amount of acetic acid released in this equimolar reaction, which was determined by titration with standard alcoholic KOH, is a measure of unsaturation originally present. Phenolphthalein was used as indicator.

The blend was further analysed by ir and thermal studies. IR spectral analysis was carried out as KBr pellets. The blend was subjected to thermal studies using DSC. The sample (10 mg) was first heated at the rate of 16°/min and subsequently cooled to low temperature. The T_g was determined as the temperature corresponding to one half the increase in heat capacity at the transition.

Results and Discussion

Qualitative and quantitative determinations of thermal modification of PVC into DHPVC in 0.5 hr foamed mass were done by uv spectral analysis. The unsaturation present in DHPVC was obtained by thermal degradation. An absorption band at 270 nm was observed with (c=1.0%) the absorbance of 0.70 for DHPVC. By comparing with the standard spectra¹¹ of H(CH=CH)_nH and by calculation⁹ using Lewis-Calvin equation, $\lambda^2 = K\eta$, it was assigned that the absorption band would correspond to 3 conjugated double bonds in a sequence of a chain containing 100 monomer units in DHPVC. The percentage of unsaturation,

3, in DHPVC was calculated and also verified by titrimetric method. The molecular weight of the unsaturated copolyester (PPPF) in 0.5 hr foamed mass was found to be 2.0×10^3 . This low molecular weight is due to the fact that the fumarate groups did not engage in homopolymerization under the normal cure conditions^{1,2}. These studies reveal the absence of formation of DHPVC-CO-PPPF copolymer upto the foaming period of 0.5 hr except the formation of unsaturation in DHPVC. Therefore, the formation of copolymer by crosslinking through the unsaturation sites of DHPVC and PPPF was suspected to occur after 30 min.

The extraction studies revealed the formation of copolymer after 30 min. The copolymer derived from the 40 min foamed sample was subjected to uv spectral analysis (1.0% concentration in DMF). An absorption band at 260.5 nm with the absorbance of 0.62 was observed. This is equivalent to 2-3 double bonds, in a sequence of a chain. From this analysis it was concluded that the deviation from the conjugation to unconjugation was at the expense of crosslinking of DHPVC with PPPF through one of the conjugated double bonds. The uv spectral analysis of the blend derived from the 40 min foamed sample also reveals the crosslinking of DHPVC and PPPF. It showed an absorption band at 260 nm with an absorbance of 0.60. The formation of the copolymer was predicted by crosslinking certain segments of PPPF with DHPVC versa by the catalytic activity of BPO. The free radicals of BPO which were trapped in polymeric fluid matrix would have initiated crosslinking. Calculated quantity of BPO was taken so that it could crosslink PPPF with DHPVC through their unsaturation. The swelling value of the copolymers decreases as the foaming period increases. This is due to the increase in crosslinking sites and subsequent graft crosslinking (Tables 2 and 3) with time. However, the degree

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF FOAMING PERIOD ON GRAFT CROSSLINKING

Sl. No.	Foaming period min	Percent graft crosslinking	Number of graft crosslinking sites (moles/moles)
1.	30	—	—
2.	40	5	0.001619
3.	50	10	0.003233
4.	60	16	0.005164
5.	70	20	0.006466
6.	80	21	0.006790

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF MOLECULAR WEIGHT AND SWELLING VALUE OF COPOLYMER ON T_g OF THE BLEND

Sl. No.	Foaming period min	Swelling value of copolymer %	\bar{M}_n of copolymer $\times 10^{-4}$	T_g of the blend
1.	30	—	—	83
2.	40	90	7.5	100
3.	50	77	8.0	115
4.	60	68	8.4	126
5.	70	61	8.8	83
6.	80	59	8.7	—

of crosslinking reaches a maximum after which no further increase in crosslinking takes place. This is due to the fact that the diffusion of unsaturated acid units of PPPF and of DHPVC towards the growing radical chains is inhibited to a greater extent by the increase in viscosity of the polymer mixture.

The copolymer thus formed would have functioned as compatibilizer for DHPVC and PPPF. The blend formation was identified from the ir spectral data of the blend which shows the presence of DHPVC and PPPF (Fig. 2).

The observed responses are 680 (C—Cl of DHPVC), 1250 (CH bending), 1610-1655 (conjugated double bond), 1414-1431 (CH=CH₂ bending), 1234 (C—O stretching), 1400 (—CH₂ bending) and 1726 cm⁻¹ (—C=O stretching of isophthalate). The compatibility of DHPVC and PPPF was finally confirmed by DSC. The variation of molecular weight (\bar{M}_n) and swelling value (%) of the copolymers with T_g of the blend are shown in Table 3. The scan obtained for the blend sample of 30 min foaming period shows a single inflection at 83° which corresponds to the T_g of DHPVC (Fig. 3). This confirms the absence of copolymer and blend formation upto 30 min. The scans obtained for the blend samples of foaming period greater than 30 min shows a trend of increase in the value of T_g upto 60 min. The scan obtained for the blend sample derived for the foaming period of 70 min also corresponds to the T_g of DHPVC. This is due to the fact that the highly crosslinked graft is not able to locate at the domain interface and provides the necessary bonding as it would if it is not highly crosslinked^{1,3}. This ultimately leads to phase segregation of individual polymer. The maximum single T_g of the DHPVC/PPPF/DHPVC-CO-PPPF blend is 126° which is attributed to the crosslinked

Fig. 2. Infrared spectra of DHPVC/PPPF/DHPVC-CO-PPPF blend.

Fig. 3. DSC scans of DHPVC/PPPF/DHPVC-CO-PPPF blend (Table 3).

copolymer of optimum molecular weight which facilitates the blending.

The properties of DHPVC-PPPF foam are tabulated (Table 4). The density of the resultant foam is medium which is a prerequisite for the design of bottom bulk head panel of the cylindrical tank, and to withstand the honeycomb delamination due to outgassing. Though the present method of foam preparation yields to medium density, blending of DHPVC and PPPF also favours to increase the density to a little extent as reported by Jacques

strength of the foam is evidently due to the residual unsaturation present in DHPVC and PPPF that remains unspent in the crosslinking process. The presence of unsaturation in the remaining mass imparts certain degree of flexibility to the cured product as can be seen in butadiene rubber.

Conclusion :

The formation of graft crosslinked copolymer and mixing of DHPVC and PPPF are simultaneous in the melt state during foaming. The foaming period was optimised to 1 hr. The compound foamed for 30 min and 70 min did not undergo blending. The absence of copolymer formation during 30 min and presence of copolymer with high molecular weight during 70 min are hysteresial to blend formation. The compound which was foamed for 1 hr and at 200° offers the desirable blend. The internal generation of the blend in foaming mass improves the properties of the foam which are essential for cryogenic insulation. The foam thus obtained is medium density with higher heat resistant and mechanical properties. The present DHPVC-PPPF foam may be used for insulation in bottom bulk head panel of cylindrical tank.

TABLE 4—PROPERTIES OF DHPVC-PPPF FOAM

Property	DHPVC-PPPF foam	Klegecell ¹⁶ H 917
1. Density (kg/m ³)	340	55
2. Resistance to heat (°C)	125	120
3. Tensile strength (kg/cm ²)	25.45	10-13
Ultimate tensile strain (%)	30.00	12-16
4. Impact strength (kg/cm)	3.20	-

*et al*¹⁴. The high temperature resistance is due to Semi Interpenetrating Network of the blend in the foamed mass. The increase in the number of crosslinking would have increased the length of the segments of the copolymer which could have penetrated into the domains of individual polymers. The blend in turn resembles a semi interpenetrating network which also gives rise to higher tensile strength and ultimate tensile strain. The impact

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JAYABALAN & BALAKRISHNAN : IDENTIFICATION AND ANALYSIS OF POLYMER BLEND

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